

PATHOLOGY OF THE AFTERBIRTH DURING 2020 IN THE BUKHARA REGIONAL PERINATAL CENTER

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ABSTRACT

Placenta, which is the main component of the system mother-placenta-fetus, occupies an important place in the birth of a healthy child. Since the placenta as a separate provision organ appears and improves depending on the mother's body, its disease also occurs depending on existing diseases in the mother's body. The aim of the study is to formulate data on the indications of placental pathologies.

Injury to the placental morphofunction is called placental insufficiency syndrome, which results in impaired fetal growth and development, and clinically increases the risk of rupture of the fetal uterine wall or may result in early fetal rupture (abortion). knowing the risk of miscarriage, lactation fullness, fibrinoid abundance, inflammation of the amniotic membranes and placental abruption, pregnancy risk, fetal developmental delay and serve as important data in predicting premature birth.

Goals and objectives.

The purpose of the study was to determine the most common pathology, consequences and prevention measures based on the pathohistological findings of the placenta in the Bukhara region. we spent a total of 370 placentas were tested in 2020.

Materials and methods.

During the examination, a total of 370 placental tissues were pathohistologically examined, based on materials from the Bukhara regional perinatal center. For general morphology, 3 pieces from each placenta, ie 1.5x1.5 cm from the center, middle and periphery, were cut and solidified in 10% neutralized formalin. After washing for 2-4 h in running water, it was dehydrated in concentrated alcohols and xylene, then paraffin was poured and the blocks were prepared. Incisions of 5-8 μ m were made from paraffin blocks and stained with hematoxylin and eosin. The examination revealed the following pathologies: Villitis - in 85 cases; short navel - in 57 cases; chorioamnionitis - in 49 cases; roller placenta - in 40 cases; funiculitis - in 35 cases; thrombosis - in 35 cases; deciduit

- in 33 cases; hypoplasia - in 10 cases;
amnionitis - in 8 cases; bacterial placentitis

- in 8 cases; bixorial placenta - detected in 3 cases.

- "Villit" - inflammation of the larynx.
- "Short umbilicus" - short development of the umbilicus (less than 32 cm).
- "Chorioamnionitis" - inflammation of the chorion and amniotic membrane.
- "Wheeled placenta" - in the early stages of pregnancy, when the edges of the placenta move, the amniotic membrane is wrapped and formed a ring.
- "Funiculitis" - inflammation of the umbilical cord.
- "Thrombosis" - a consequence of circulatory disorders in the placenta.
- "Detsiduit" - inflammation of the decidual membrane.
- "Hypoplasia" - underdevelopment of the placenta. (400gr and less)
- "Amnionitis" - inflammation of the amniotic membrane.
- "Bacterial placentitis" - placenta inflammation caused by bacteria.

- "Bixorial biamnion placenta" - in twins each has a separate amnion and chorion, 2 placentas are attached to each other.

Conclusions.

The results of pathohistological examinations of the placenta showed that in most cases, villitis pathology was observed in the placenta. Short umbilical cord, chorioamnionitis, valvular placental pathologies were more common.

Villitis is the transmission of microorganisms through the blood (hematogenous) to placental tissue and damage to the chorionic villus, the etiology of which in most cases (95%) is unknown. Villitis causes growth retardation, stillbirth, and the development of preeclampsia, hypertension, and autoimmune diseases in pregnant women.

Short umbilical cord - does not always lead to complications during pregnancy, but can

be dangerous during childbirth. As a result, complications of the birth process, impaired fetal heart rate, acute hypoxia, and ischemic conditions in the brain may occur.

Chorioamnionitis is the cause of damage to the amniotic fluid as a result of external road infections. It serves as a signal to end the labor process as soon as possible. The result can lead to postpartum endometritis. Valiksimon is one of the anomalies of the placenta-placenta shape. In the early stages of pregnancy, due to the separation of the edges of the placenta from the uterus, uterine bleeding, changes in the shape of the placenta, the area of necrotic tissue is covered with fibrin fibers.

These data open up a real prospect of a significant reduction in perinatal morbidity and mortality and provide undoubtedly useful information not only for pathologists, but also for all specialists involved in the diagnosis, prevention and treatment of obstetric and neonatal diseases.

- Detected pathologies are often characterized by a complex set of circulatory, dystrophic, immune, inflammatory, compensatory-adaptive, involuntal reactions, always inconsistent clinical data on the development of pregnancy and the condition of the newborn with ultrasound data, pathomorphological findings latest and real information not only proves that it is, but also shows that every placenta tissue must undergo a pathological examination.

- These data are also necessary for neonatologists for a rational clinical interpretation of the etiology of pathology and pathomorphological examination of the child after childbirth and can help to improve the performance of obstetric institutions at any level.

- Many questions about the condition of the fetoplacental system can be solved during a qualified macroscopic examination of the placenta.

Wheeled placenta.
Short navel.

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